

FOODITY

D4.1 – FOODITY Impact Master Plan

Prepared by AUSTRALO

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Abstract

This document provides a detailed overview of FOODITY's communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy, essential components of any successful Horizon Europe funded project, and defines the objectives, priorities, and potential implementation strategies to achieve all desired outcomes. Additionally, FOODITY's Impact Master Plan outlines the resources, methods, and platforms to use in order to successfully disseminate project activities, successes, and quantifiable results to targeted audiences, serving as the basis for the market adoption of the FOODITY solutions and innovations.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
CTA	Call to Action
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information Technology
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PR	Press Release
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

The FOODITY project

The main goal of FOODITY is to create a European ecosystem of digital solutions that contributes to a more sustainable and healthy food and nutrition system — respecting citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty.

FOODITY will run a **2M€ pilot development programme for creating 12 data-driven solutions** to demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while guaranteeing the user's full control and ownership over their personal data.

These innovations will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the four Food 20301 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: (1) Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (2) Food systems supporting a healthy planet, (3) Circularity and resource efficiency, and (4) Innovation and empowering communities.

Participants in the pilot development programme will be selected through two open calls to be launched in the second semester of 2023. Eligible beneficiaries will be research and technology organisations (RTOs) and universities, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), social innovation actors and training organisations.

The programme will provide its beneficiaries with a set of value-added services: from one-to-one mentoring to training on technical, business, and legal matters, as well as technical and financial support (up to 187.500€ per beneficiary) for developing their pilots.

During the next three years (January 2023 - December 2025), the FOODITY consortium, comprised of 7 partners, will join forces to make this a reality.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable sets the framework, guidelines and means for the project's **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities**. The proposed document also serves to design and build an ad hoc Stakeholder Collaboration Framework, developed to identify the ecosystem of entities impacted by FOODITY's innovations and findings.

The **strategies** set out in this document aim to:

- Ensure the development of appropriate means of communication of the project's results outside of its consortium, with the intention of raising awareness.
- Increase the project's impact on the identified target audiences for further commercial and research purposes.
- Foster stakeholders' engagement with the consortium to give consistency and continuity to the project's findings and expected outcomes.

Moreover, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plans will also serve an internal purpose for consortium members to always be aware of outreach activities pursued by other partners. These plans will be subject to constant evaluation and revision throughout the duration of the FOODITY project, to always have an updated and accurate depiction of the progress made and challenges ahead.

1 Introduction

This document outlines the initial FOODITY Impact Master Plan. It includes the overall project dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies and kick starts the stakeholder engagement strategy, which will be the basis for community building and impact generation.

The plan results from a collaborative effort between partners, considering stakeholders' categories and needs as well as partners' communication channels and tools. This means that it is a tool that assists each partner in maximising the impact of their own dissemination efforts while also giving ways to guarantee high visibility of project-related activities and results.

This plan proposes a list of suitable communication and dissemination tools and activities for engaging the target groups in the project. To this end, a multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy is proposed to maximise the impact of the dissemination activities, adjusting the materials and tools to the specific needs, interests, and potential for involvement of the target audience.

The FOODITY consortium views this as a living document and strategy that reflects open, ongoing communication with potential users and related networks throughout the project to be inclusive and guarantee the best outcomes and impact.

2 Agile Stakeholder Management

2.1 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant stakeholders is an activity often referred to as ‘community building’ and it is a key aspect of every Horizon Europe project, (as the preceding Horizon 2020 programme), FOODITY being no exception. Indeed, the programme relies on communities, initiatives, and projects that will either use the outcomes or relate to and possibly liaise with its activities along its course.

Creating and nurturing an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is a crucial factor in the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholder’s impact on a project depends on its potential power - the ability to influence the value proposition - and the interest in exercising that power. Assessing the stakeholder’s impact on FOODITY will help to decide where to devote time and effort to achieve the greatest benefits.

To address fundamental innovation challenges, adopting an open framework of collaboration with peers and groups is imperative. This approach will allow FOODITY to better understand the requirements and benefits of aligning efforts with similar task forces, creating new synergies, and extending our range of action.

Engagement Framework

To maximise the effectiveness of the dissemination, communication and exploitation plans that will be introduced in this document, the consortium requires a systematic management mechanism of the ever-changing list of organisations, initiatives, and players with a position to influence the value streams of the project.

For this reason, FOODITY will implement the **Agile Marketing Lab Framework**®, a methodology designed by AUSTRALO and based on an Agile Stakeholder Engagement framework (Figure 1), designed to continuously develop and strengthen relationships with a significant audience through the values of the **Agile Manifesto**¹ (Table 1):

Table 1. Agile Manifesto Principles

The Agile Manifesto Principles		
Individuals and interactions	over	processes and tools
Results		comprehensive documentation
Collaboration		formality
Responding to change		following a plan

¹ <http://agilemanifesto.org/>

- **Individuals and interactions over processes and tools:** Ecosystem building is a team-based strategy to produce value through collaboration. Projects need tools, but the team must also operate well together through fruitful interactions with the stakeholders.
- **Results over comprehensive documentation:** It is much more valuable to interact with the stakeholders, obtain continuous feedback, and manage increments of the ecosystem's snapshot rather than overspending resources on studying and reporting about their profiles and potential objectives.
- **Collaboration over formality:** This framework aims to encourage and make the programme's cooperation easier. The team wants to involve and work with stakeholders to examine and adapt the vision so that the project is as beneficial as possible.
- **Responding to change over following a plan:** This methodology places more emphasis on creating an ecosystem of interested parties over the course of the project than on keeping a static vision of the stakeholders.

The framework (Figure 1) follows an iterative implementation structure based on **Sprints**, which are time-boxes of 6 months where the main goal is to continuously increase and reinforce the engagement of the stakeholders with the initiative. A new Sprint starts immediately after the conclusion of the previous. Its workflow includes the following phases:

Figure 1. Stakeholder Engagement Framework

- **Phase 1 – Analysis:** Building upon the objectives of FOODITY, this phase will explore, map, and assess Target Groups - and specific candidates - with different degrees of relevance for the scope and impact of the work plan. FOODITY will build upon the sound experience and active involvement of the consortium members in initiatives and players that must be considered as a baseline for engagement, taking advantage of new leads

generated by second-degree partnerships and new opportunities as an outcome of the Interaction phase, including emerging initiatives and Horizon Europe projects. The key result will be an initial version of the 'Stakeholder Map', a graphical instrument to 1) list key actors and specific candidates within them; 2) thoughtfully organise and correlate these audiences; 3) define a common terminology to be used in all the project's reference.

- **Phase 2 – Interaction:** The following phase will involve the engagement with the identified target groups in a manner that supports the initiatives described in the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation strategies. In this stage, FOODITY will work with those initiatives deemed particularly significant. Such interaction will include:
 - Lead generation – a one-to-many approach on prospective building awareness and lead generation over time, reaching out to a critical mass of players.
 - Prospecting – one-to-one actions focused on a specific set of prospects of the target audience. This type of interaction will include individual email exchanges, meetings, and follow-up actions.

Whenever relevant, the project will formally join specific Task Forces and Working Groups, contribute to scientific publications, and participate in events. Feedback extrapolated from previous Sprints will be used to enhance the efficiency and impact of these measures.

- **Phase 3 – Learning:** The key component of an agile process is incorporating the lessons discovered during execution, thereby fuelling the next iteration with the knowledge to improve the plan. The consortium will therefore draw conclusions and learn from the activities taken throughout the engagement and use those discoveries to inform the next Sprint. Additionally, this will include findings from interviews and quick questionnaires, as well as information gathered from outside sources about the project and its operation. FOODITY will adapt the channels and measures from 'Interaction' to new specific needs and opportunities.

2.1.1 Target Audience and Stakeholders

Promoting FOODITY and encouraging stakeholders to engage with the project requires understanding who the 'target audiences' are (Figure 2). Understanding these profiles and their influence in the value chain is essential to crafting the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plans.

Figure 2. FOODITY Target Audience

Food Value Chain Actors

This category includes the food system actors (producers, distributors, retailers):

- Agricultural **production** entities, food manufacturing companies and companies providing access to the market for food manufacturers, **distributors and retailers**. These can be engaged through intermediary organisations such as:
 - [CELCAA, the European Liaison Committee for Agricultural and Agri-Food Trade](#): umbrella organisation representing European-level associations and companies active in agricultural and agri-food trading. Including wholesale traders (collectors, distributors, storers, importers and exporters) delivering agricultural and agri-food products as feed materials to farmers and the compound feed industry, as well as raw material to the food industry, as food and drink to retailers.
 - [COPA-COGECA](#): union of the two big agricultural umbrella organisations COPA and COGECA and the voice of farmers and agri-cooperatives in the EU.

- [FoodDrinkEurope](#) - representing Europe's food and drink manufacturers.
- [Primary Food Processors](#) - association for the European primary food processing industry.
- [Independent Retail Europe](#) - European association that acts as an umbrella organisation for groups of independent retailers in the food and non-food sectors.

Social Innovation Actors and Associations Representing the Voice of Consumers

Social innovation actors aiming at citizen empowerment, proposing concrete actions for raising awareness of citizens' data rights, and associations representing consumers' interest in food and nutrition. Examples of these actors are:

- **Consumer associations**, such as:
 - [Consumer Protection Cooperation](#) (CPC) - network of authorities responsible for the enforcement of EU consumer protection laws.
 - [VKI](#) - Austrian Consumer Association.
 - [Spanish Organic Consumers Association](#).
 - [FACUA](#) - Spanish Consumer Association.
 - [LANDARE](#) - Association of Consumers of Organic Products.
- **Citizens' data rights associations**
 - [DATA RIGHTS](#) - non-profit organisation that defends, enforces, and advances data rights.
 - [DATA for GOOD Foundation](#) - non-profit organisation that promotes individual data rights.
 - [Cities Coalition for Digital Rights](#).
- **Entities defending causes** such as:
 - the rights of the consumers to a healthy and nutritious diet.
 - just distribution of wealth in food system actors, leading to fair remuneration of food producers.

Some of these entities are:

 - [Safe Food Advocacy Europe](#).
 - [Federation of European Nutrition Societies](#).
 - [Good Food Good Farming](#) - civil society alliance that campaigns for sustainable food and farming across Europe.
 - [Compassion in world farming](#).
 - [Foodwatch](#) - European advocacy group that focuses on protecting consumer rights as they pertain to food quality.
- **Entities striving to raise awareness** for:
 - Healthier diets.

- Fighting obesity.
- Reduction of food waste.
- Minimisation of the environmental impact of food production and distribution.

Some of these entities are:

- [Slow Food International](#).
- [European Association for the Study of Obesity](#) (EASO).
- [EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub](#).
- [Zero Waste Europe](#) (ZWE).

The project will capitalise on the participation of the consortium in strategic networks with an active involvement of citizens in research, such as:

- The [European Citizen Science Association](#) (ECSA).
- [Allianz for Responsible Science](#).
- [European Science Engagement Association](#) (EUSEA).

Entrepreneurial and Research Ecosystem

This category includes actors such as:

- **Startups and SMEs** developing solutions for data-driven innovation, including personalised nutrition solutions for online food retail and food delivery.
- **Multiplier organisations to reach Startups and SMEs**, such as incubators, accelerators, and other support actors.
- **Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)** and universities working on advancing the state of the art and solving the challenges around data-driven innovation for food and nutrition and mechanisms to preserve citizens' sovereignty of their personal data in using solutions for food and nutrition.
- or **Technology enthusiasts who develop digital and data-driven solutions for food and nutrition.**

All of these in areas such as:

- Personalised nutrition
- Online food retail
- Digital tracking of food and nutrition-related consumer behaviour
- Home delivery of food
- Food advertising

Also, **training organisations** providing professional training for careers in the food industry, such as culinary or nutrition schools, interested in teaching and experimenting with the power of data for innovation and competitiveness in food production and diet planning.

Hence, FOODITY will engage with **research-oriented institutions** (technical universities, RTOs, spin-offs) as well as **business-driven organisations** (startups, SMEs) and **social innovation actors** (NGOs, associations), which will:

- Contribute to the technical ambition of the project;
- Contribute to defining potential challenges, leading to more demand-driven solutions;
- Represent the target audience for the open call campaigns.

Partnerships and Networks

FOODITY intends to leverage the knowledge and outreach capacity of initiatives in the food and nutrition arena, and the data sphere. The consortium's participation in active ecosystems will help create synergies and reinforce awareness of the open calls and project outputs, such as:

- Together with FOODITY, another project has been funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01 topic, with who we are cooperating to create bonds of mutual knowledge and expertise:
 - [DRG4Food](#) - Empowering a fair and responsible European FoodRegister, fostering citizen sovereignty and creating a data-driven food system. It is important to note that at this stage there is already a collaboration framework in place with DRG4FOOD. The collaboration focuses on promotion activities, open calls, stakeholder activities, and others.
- Moreover, other Horizon Europe-funded projects, operating and researching in FOODITY-related domains (*Informed consumer choices; Healthy and safe foods and diets for all; citizen empowerment, Food systems, Data Sovereignty*), are also key stakeholder groups with which the project will seek to create active synergies. Some examples of these projects are:
 - [FOODPathS](#) - Co-creating the prototype 'Sustainable FOOD Systems PARtnersHip'
 - [FOOD TRAILS](#) - Building pathways towards FOOD 2030-led urban food policies
 - SMART -
 - [CITIES2030](#) - Co-creating resilient and susTainable food systEms towards FOOD2030
 - [CLEVERFOOD](#) - Connected Labs for Empowering Versatile Engagement in Radical Food system transformation
 - [Stance4Health](#) - Smart Technologies for personAlised Nutrition and Consumer Engagement
 - [SWITCH](#) - Switching European food systems for a just, healthy, and sustainable dietary transition through knowledge and innovation
 - [FoodSHIFT2030](#) - Food System Hubs Innovating towards Fast Transition by 2030
 - [FOODSAFETY4EU](#) - Multi-Stakeholder Platform for Food Safety in Europe

- [PLAN'EAT](#) - Food Systems Transformation Towards Healthy and Sustainable Dietary Behaviour
- [FNS-Cloud](#) - Food Nutrition Security Cloud
- From the technical point of view, FOODITY builds on two recent R&I H2020-funded actions:
 - The [PROTEIN project](#), which will provide state-of-the-art tools and software components as building blocks for the development of personalised nutrition solutions.
 - The [PoSeID-on project](#), which will provide a deployment-ready solution for trustworthy secure large-scale data-sharing transactions.
- FOODITY will also build on the experience of the consortium in projects involving social innovation practices, such as [NewHoRRizon](#); [ProFuture](#) or [BLOOM](#); and others related to the development of distributed and open platforms for citizen-friendly data governance, such as [DECODE](#) or [LEDGER](#) (NGI).
- European partnerships and networks related to the agrifood sector, such as:
 - [EIT Food](#) - accelerates innovation to build a future-fit food system that produces healthy and sustainable food for all
 - [EIP-AGRI](#) - The agricultural European Innovation Partnership
 - [agROBOTfood](#) - Connecting Robotic Technologies with a dynamic agrifood network of DIHs
 - [SmartAgriHubs](#)
- European partnerships and associations advocating for data and digital technologies, such as [Big Data Value Association](#), [Gaia-X European Data Infrastructure](#), where the consortium is present or their broad experience participating in the [Next Generation Internet Initiative](#) (NGI), aimed at shaping the development and evolution of the Internet into an Internet of Humans, where several partners hold an active role on various present and past Research and Innovation Actions such as [NGI Explorers](#), [NGI Sargasso](#), [NGI DAPSI](#) (Data Portability and Services Incubator), [NGI TrustChain](#) (Fostering a Human-Centred, Trustworthy and Sustainable Internet) or [NGI TruBlo](#) (supporting innovation towards trusted and reliable content on future blockchains). All of which can help attract top-level talents as applicants for the open calls.
- Ecosystems concentrating large number of SMEs, including:
 - [Enterprise Europe Network](#) – one of the most relevant networks for supporting innovative SMEs in Europe, with 600+ active member organisations in 60+ countries worldwide.

- [European Digital Innovation Hubs](#) (EDIHS) – pan European network of one-stop shops that help companies become more competitive regarding their business/production processes, products or services using digital technologies.
- [EU Innovation Council](#)
- Acceleration and incubation programmes linked to the consortium, such as:
 - [REACH](#) - European-wide second-generation incubator for data-fuelled startups and SMEs that aims to facilitate the development of trusted and secure innovative solutions based on industrial and personal data.
 - [DMS Accelerator](#) - Support programme for startups working with data.
 - IRSUS - Business support and training programme.
- Regional clusters linked to the consortium, such as:
 - Deep Tech French cluster [Systematic Paris-Region](#)

Policy makers

Policy makers at the national and European level interested in receiving feedback on the policies and initiatives, namely regarding the challenges of using personal data for data-driven innovation, particularly in the food and nutrition sector.

Especially relevant are the developments within the following EU priorities:

- A [Europe fit for the digital age](#):
 - The [European data strategy](#).
- The [European Green Deal](#):
 - [Farm to Fork Strategy](#), for a fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food system.
 - The [New European Bauhaus](#), the interdisciplinary initiative situated at the crossroads between social inclusion, science, and technology.
- The [Food 2030](#), the EC Research and Innovation Policy to make our food systems ready for the future. It is in line with and supports the goals of the European Green Deal, Farm to Fork strategy and bioeconomy strategy.
- And, in general, the [UN Sustainable Development Goals](#) and the Digital Responsibility Goals.

In order to be able to promote the FOODITY results relevant for this stakeholder, and encourage engagement, the project will capitalise on several actions:

- The consortium's participation in initiatives such as the [Austrian platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation](#).
- Contributing to **policy task forces or working groups** (where and when relevant) shaping policies related to food and nutrition. In this area we can highlight the following interactions:

- Regarding FOOD 2030, FOODITY will take part in the activities organised by the [FOOD 2030 group hosted within the Sustainable Food Systems Network](#). This group serves as the main networking tool and organizational hub for cross-project collaboration within the FOOD 2030 Network. It fosters collective action and concrete initiatives across vertical themes, while also providing regular updates on events and opportunities to keep all members informed and connected. This group, aside from the opportunity of participating in joint events and workshops, appearing in the FOOD 2030 Networks Newsletter, **the project will be able to share its results in a space called the “Drop-It hub”, where members add links to resources they want to share, which also feeds into the FOOD 2030 Online Platform.** Due to its relevance, the Sustainable Food Systems Network created a **subgroup on Policy and Governance for Food System Transformation**. This subgroup is dedicated to organise national policy dialogues, cooperate for international policy events, collaborate on policy briefs and exchange knowledge to make the most of each member’s expertise and **project results, which can be shared with the group for the creation of synergies of seeking feedback.**
- Regarding the **Digital Sustainable Goals**, FOODITY will lean on the interaction and synergies created with its sister project [DRG4FOOD](#), which have these Goals as a centre aspect of their strategy.

Society

The general public should not be overlooked. FOODITY will encourage a common understanding and trust of the positive impact of data and digital solutions in the food and nutrition sectors, shifting the focus from technology-driven progress to a thoroughly human-centric and sustainable approach.

Hence, highly accessible content will be produced to engage with society (making it available across social media, newsletters, awareness publications, etc.), especially targeting European citizens:

- Concerned by their level of trust in data-driven solutions for food and nutrition.
- Interested in the latest developments at the technological level.

And aimed at improving their control over their personal data when adopting these solutions.

2.2 Stakeholders Map

Figure 3 contains the first version of the FOODITY Stakeholders Map, which graphically summarises all the target audiences at this stage. This diagram has been defined by considering the different target stakeholders’ groups identified so far as the outcome of the ongoing Sprint of the Agile Stakeholder Framework.

Figure 3. FOODITY Stakeholders Map

3 Dissemination and Communication

Dissemination and Communication in Innovation Projects are key and necessary elements for achieving their desired impact. According to the European Commission:

“Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players, and policymakers. By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.”²

“Communication in Research and Innovation projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures to communicate to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”³

3.1 Dissemination Plan

To this end, **FOODITY has developed a flexible and adjustable Dissemination Plan** that aims at building effective awareness of the project results, creating understanding, and aiming for action among the key target audience identified. The execution of this strategy will facilitate the best use and uptake of the outcomes and research insights generated throughout the project’s lifetime, reinforcing each of the impacts in the work plan.

3.1.1 The ‘3 phases’ approach

Dissemination activities will be carried out in **three main phases** (Figure 4). Each of these has specific objectives and will therefore perform different actions using the appropriate channels. These phases will be presented and discussed during the first months of the project and will be refined accordingly to **match the priorities of FOODITY**.

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm1

Figure 4. Dissemination Plan Phases

Phase I: Analysis (M01-M06). In this preliminary phase, the consortium will analyse the project's framework, with special attention to internal and external barriers and obstacles that could slow down the dissemination activities. It will also define the priorities and actions for the first half of the project.

The project's dissemination and communication leader, AUSTRALO, organises the engagement activities to match dissemination and communication efforts with the needs of the identified stakeholders and raise public awareness of the project's goals and expected results.

During this phase, the FOODITY dissemination plan is prepared and executed, along with the branding, website, social media, and the first set of promotional materials produced.

Phase II: Increase impact (M06-M18). The main objective of Phase II is to increase the awareness generated during Phase I, with a **special focus on the first Open Call of the FOODITY Pilot Programme**, as well as to expose the main FOODITY achievements up to that point.

The Dissemination and Communication Leader will adapt the channels and measures identified in the proposal phase (and refined during Phase I) to the specific needs of Phase II, and it will work to properly find the right means to engage and collaborate with the target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project's results.

Participation in workshops, organisation of ad hoc events, as well as tutorials/webinars (if needed) will boost the dissemination process. Specific press release (PR) material will also be produced.

Phase III: Adoption (M19-M36). This phase will leverage the general awareness raised in Phase I and II, this time with a **special focus on the second Open Call**, as well as attracting more potential target segments to the FOODITY results, to increase the impact **and sustainability of the project outcomes**.

First, the Dissemination, Communication Leader (AUSTRALO), and the Exploitation Leader (F6S) will evaluate the outcomes of Phase I and II and, if needed, AUSTRALO will refine the priorities, channels and measures previously settled, also in concertation with the agile stakeholder management activities. Secondly, it will define the main activities that could increase the impact beyond the project's lifetime, such as continuing use of events, participation in workshops and conferences, and contributions to publications in targeted specific online media and printed trade and research journals.

3.1.2 Objectives

The main and key objectives of the dissemination strategy are as follows:

- To set up the information dissemination mechanisms and priorities of FOODITY.
- To establish, maintain and grow a community around FOODITY in coordination with the stakeholder management framework.
- To create visibility and promote the work and results for target stakeholders by creating promotional material and information campaigns.
- To disseminate projects and outcomes to the widest possible community through various channels and instruments. External participation and knowledge sharing will be encouraged through networking activities and events aimed at increasing the impact potential and enriching the contribution to the project.
- To liaise with other EU, national and international initiatives to maximise the impact.

3.1.3 Measures

To execute the dissemination plan, the consortium has identified several measures that need to be implemented throughout the project, enabling it to reach the above-mentioned objectives in the most efficient and effective way. In Table 2, the **dissemination material** is outlined:

Table 2. Dissemination Material

MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Target Stakeholders
Project Documentation	Material describing and reporting on technical outputs, APIs, architectures, guidelines, models, recommendations, handbooks, promotional activities, and other insights acquired.	Publicly available information which can be disseminated and infused similar to FOODITY initiatives and to the community as a whole.	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovators, Policymakers
Peer-reviewed Publications	Over 10 peer-reviewed scientific articles in top	Ensure the project's technical achievements and experimental	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem

MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Target Stakeholders
	refereed scientific journals and conferences.	findings will be known and exploited by the larger research community and related scientific domains.	
Non-scientific Publications	Release and contribute to over 30 publications ; blog posts, articles, insight papers, citizen factsheets and any other non-scientific publication oriented to end-users and the public society.	Widespread awareness about its open calls, nutrition for sustainable healthy diets, climate and environment, circularity and resource efficiency and innovation and empowerment of communities among a broad audience.	ALL Stakeholders
Practice Abstracts	End-user material will be produced in the form of 50 summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format "practice abstracts".	Feed the innovative knowledge from this project into the EIP-AGRI website for broad dissemination to practitioners.	Food Value Chain, Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem
Coding Guidelines	Guidelines will be produced, including 'code of conduct', 'development environment', 'security guidelines', 'coding style', 'debugging' and performance considerations.	Facilitate general guidelines to ease external development efforts.	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem

In Table 3, the **dissemination channels** are explained:

Table 3. Digital Dissemination Channels

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Target Stakeholders
Source Code Repository	Make accessible its software repositories through well-known source code management platforms. For this, the project will use GitHub or GitLab.	This measure will encourage other Tech providers to re-use the outcomes easily.	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem
Open Access to Research	A Zenodo FOODITY community has been created, an online repository to manage and publish material with different access permissions, including peer-reviewed publications, shareable scientific research data, and other resources.	Encourage open access publishing platform for scientific articles among the consortium, with no author fees and compliant with open access requirements.	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovators
Helpdesk	Email support via a generic contact point (contact@foodity.eu), including bug tracking and feature requests and a FAQ section on the website. Additionally, the project will dedicate specific channels for technical support to third parties, such as email opencall@foodity.eu	Common problem-solving.	ALL Stakeholders

Table 4 provides an indicative list of **events** that have been identified as main targets. This list is continuously updated by all project partners while actions per event and per partner are being identified and assigned, depending on the maturity of the project.

Table 4. Dissemination Events

EVENTS			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Target Stakeholders
Webinars / Workshops	FOODITY will co-organise 16 webinars and workshops during the project's lifetime as a means of transferring and exchanging technical and socio-economic knowledge with the community, with a total of 1,000 unique participants.	Workshops will facilitate hands-on training and exchange of ideas, providing opportunities for round table discussions, mentoring and co-design.	Food Value Chain, Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovators, Partnerships and Networks
Conferences / Fairs	Participating in conferences and trade fairs is a strategic mechanism to interact actively with multiple stakeholders.	Showcase results achieved by the project through presentations, talks, exhibition spaces and personal engagement in at least 30 events.	ALL Stakeholders

The following list (Table 5) introduces some of the **conferences** that the project will emphasise. However, this list is dynamic and gets updated on a frequent basis according to the scientific and technical maturity of the project.

Table 5. Identified events interesting for FOODITY

IDENTIFIED CONFERENCES	
Event	Short Description
Smart Agrifood Summit	The largest European event for innovation and digitisation of the agrifood chain.
Farm2Fork Conference	The Farm to Fork conference focuses on the progress made in the implementation of the Farm to Fork Strategy . The event also provides a forum for discussion on the challenges and opportunities linked to the global transition to sustainable food systems, and on further thematic areas of intervention and ongoing research and innovation efforts.

IDENTIFIED CONFERENCES	
Event	Short Description
European Food Safety Forum	Forum gathering Food Safety System actors to share knowledge and best practices, discuss the Food Safety hot issues, and propose collaborations for improving the efficacy of Food Safety policies and research in Europe.
EIT events	<p>The European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) aims to strengthen Europe's ability to innovate. Among its several communities, two have relevance for FOODITY regarding the attendance to events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EIT Food is Europe's leading food innovation initiative, working to make the food system more sustainable, healthy, and trusted. EIT Food events calendar, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Agrifood Innovation Summit ○ EIT Food Annual Event ○ Future of Food Conference • EIT Digital event: Grow Digital.
ISPIM Innovation Conference	The ISPIM Innovation Conference brings together innovation management professionals from research, industry, and intermediary organisations. The conference format includes facilitated themed sessions for academic and practitioner presentations, discussion panels and workshops, and excellent networking opportunities.
European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production and Cleaner Production (ERSCP)	The ERSCP Society seeks to encourage stakeholders to work on new ideas of Sustainable Consumption and Production to promote the transition to sustainable societies. ERSCP brings together stakeholders from Europe and across the world, and Roundtable Conferences and other meetings hosted by different countries. Roundtables aim to combine research sessions with interactive sessions and workshops designed to provide optimal opportunities to exchange knowledge and experience, develop new project ideas and networks, find new cooperation partners, and establish new collaborations.
Food Analytics Conference	Conference on Analytical Technologies for Food Quality and Sustainable Food Production.
PETRA Conference	Hosted by CERTH, the PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA) conference is an interdisciplinary conference that focuses on computational and engineering approaches to improve the quality of life and enhance human performance in a range of settings.
SME oriented events	
Web Summit	One of Europe's largest technology events.

IDENTIFIED CONFERENCES	
Event	Short Description
South Summit	Startup encounter that gathers leading companies, startups and entrepreneurs, and the investment community to create business opportunities and valuable connections
EU SME Week	A pan-European campaign that aims to promote entrepreneurship in Europe. It helps existing entrepreneurs find information on available support and tries to encourage more people to set up their own businesses. The main event is organised every autumn together with the SME Assembly and the European enterprise promotion awards ceremony.
4YFN	4YFN is the startup event of the world's largest exhibition for the mobile industry, GSMA MWC. Its goal is to support startups, investors, and companies to connect and launch new business ventures.
Codemotion	Conference gathering for developers and IT professionals craving for insights on the latest technologies, inspirational talks, and hands-on activities.
Techchill	TechChill, one of the largest Baltic Tech events, is taking place in April 2023, bringing together international and local investors, founders, and ecosystem players.

3.2 Communication Plan

In the case of FOODITY, **Communication activities involve specific measures for promoting the project itself and the results attained.** The communication plan has the mission to reach out to a broader audience beyond the project's core community.

The plan herein has the mission to reach out to the broadest audience possible. Communication campaigns will be implemented throughout the project lifetime to efficiently build traction among the target audience, emphasising **FOODITY innovations and pilots' and third parties' activities.** Such campaigns will build upon the **Promotion Mix** - the fourth element of the **Marketing Mix**⁴ (Figure 5) - that focuses on creating awareness and persuading the audience to engage. In FOODITY, this Promotion Mix is the integration of:

- **Personal Selling:** Personal selling is based on developing relationships with the people of our target audience to promote our project and its results. It focuses on understanding their needs and demonstrating how FOODITY can bring them value. In our case, it will mainly involve one-to-one meetings as well as mailing campaigns.

⁴ <https://neilpatel.com/blog/4-ps-of-marketing/>

- **Digital Marketing:** Digital marketing is a broad and continuously evolving concept, ranging from the strategies we carry out on the project's website to those we develop on our social networks or content marketing. At FOODITY, the digital channels used to promote the project will be its website, social networks, newsletters, among others.
- **Promotional Material:** The aim of promotional material is to help promote the progress of a project, as well as interesting and revealing information about the people and aspects related to it. At FOODITY, we will create both online (banners, infographics, videos, etc.) and offline materials (flyers, brochures, roll-ups, etc.), which will be disseminated through our channels and at the events and conferences participated. The consortium partners will have access to them and will be able to disseminate them through their channels and in the D&C actions they carry out. Occasionally, these materials will be shared with external partners to help us reach new audiences.
- **Branding:** The branding of a project is oriented to make it easily recognizable. It includes the elements that must always be used in all existing formats and channels. At FOODITY, we have updated the initially proposed logo and defined all branding elements and templates to be used.

Figure 5. The Marketing Mix

FOODITY, as a project funded by the Horizon Europe Programme, has an **obligation to “promote the action and its results”, according to Article 17 of the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement**⁵. The key aspects of this obligation are explained in Figure 6.

⁵ Horizon Europe Annotated Grant Agreement: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

Why communicate?

- ✓ Attract the best experts to your team
- ✓ Share best practices with others
- ✓ Promote your project’s activities and results
- ✓ Trigger new collaborations & opportunities
- ✓ Generate market demand for the products or services developed
- ✓ Raise citizens’ awareness of how their money is spent
- ✓ Show the success of European collaboration
- ✓ It is a legal obligation

Article 17 of the Horizon Europe grant agreement: Obligation to promote the action and its results

Beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner (including to the public).

Build your own communication strategy

- Be strategic:** allocate resources, involve professional communicators and ensure continuity.
- Set your goals and objectives:** make clear what you want to achieve with your communication strategy, and how.
- Define your audience:** include all relevant target groups and tailor your content to each audience. Do you have a media list relevant to your area?
- Choose your message:** is it news? Share it with your audience. Keep it simple and remember to tell a story; do not just list the facts.
- Use a channel that will reach your target audience.** Remember to let your Project Officer and National Contact Point know about your achievements!
- Evaluate your efforts:** set simple indicators to measure your success.

Communicate your project

A comprehensive communication strategy is crucial to promote your project and its results. Your plan should define clear objectives adapted to a range of target audiences. It should be proportionate to the scale of your project.

Go digital:

- Website, videos
- Social media (your account and your institution’s)
- Newsletters
- Factsheets

Build networks:

- Events (i.e. conferences, symposia)
- Project & experts meetings
- Reach out to the media

HORIZON EUROPE

Figure 6. European Commission Communication Principles⁶

⁶ European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, Are you communicating your Horizon Europe project?, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022 <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/078892>

3.2.1 Objectives

The main objectives of the communication strategy are as follows:

- Set up internal communication mechanisms among the partners of the consortium.
- Support the external promotion of FOODITY and its outcomes, managing the branding.
- Deliver top-level messages about the project to all identified and relevant stakeholders.
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of FOODITY and its activities.
- Increase awareness and interest in the project.

3.2.2 Measures

A series of measures and communication tools (Table 6, Table 7, and Table 8) will be implemented to allow the project to reach the right audiences in a communication-friendly and synchronous way.

Table 6. Communication - Personal Channels

PERSONAL SELLING			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Email Campaigns	Implementing targeted email campaigns to stakeholders to raise awareness about the project and its activities. EU GDPR-compliant solutions will be used. A portfolio of templates per target will be produced, integrating CTAs.	Broadcasting messages to a target pool of contact points via email is a highly effective measure for promoting activities and results, seeking endorsement for the open calls.	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovation and Associations, Partnerships and Networks, Policymakers
One-to-one Meetings	Follow up action with targeted stakeholders to engage them in future activities and maintain a constant communication flow.	Although this is not a scalable mechanism, one-to-one online or phone calls and meetings are successful when targeting very specific key actors, often as a follow-up of an email campaign, scouting or event. For the scope of the project, this is especially relevant when engaging	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovation and Associations, Partnerships and Networks, Policymakers

PERSONAL SELLING			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
		<p>policymakers, SMEs managers (open calls) or representatives from Partnerships and Networks.</p>	

Table 7. Communication - Digital Marketing

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Project Website	<p>Establish online presence, a website where the general public and interested individuals can read about the project's progress and findings, including news, results, events, and Open Calls.</p> <p>See https://foodity.eu/</p>	<p>A key instrument for enhancing the visibility of the project, introducing visitors to FOODITY's rationale and educating them about the project concept.</p>	ALL Stakeholders
Open Call Platform	<p>The F6S platform will be used to host and run the open calls operations.</p>	<p>The platform counts with a critical mass of 16K members.</p>	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovation and Associations
Sploro Mentoring Platform	<p>The SPLORO platform will be used to host the value-added services programme.</p>	<p>The platform counts with tools to monitor and analyse the progress of the selected beneficiaries.</p>	Entrepreneurs
Social Media	<p>FOODITY will create and actively maintain its presence in a number of social media channels, with a particular focus on Twitter and LinkedIn, as they have proven to be the most effective tools when engaging with tech communities.</p>	<p>Social media channels are a fast and low-cost way of reaching interest groups and communities that are normally not present at any events or conferences (physical or digital).</p>	ALL Stakeholders

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Newsletters	<p>Complementary to email engagement, online newsletters will provide a snapshot of the main activities and achievements of the project. The project will design and publish quarterly e-newsletters, while contributing with content to another 6 external newsletters of reference to the sector.</p> <p>Professional marketing platforms will be used to automate the distribution among all contact points.</p>	<p>The project newsletter shows the progress of the project to all stakeholders and keeps their interest high.</p>	ALL Stakeholders
Press Releases	<p>FOODITY will develop and distribute press releases to mainstream and specialist media as well as relevant civil society newsletters, magazines, and journals. Press releases will also be distributed individually by partners to communicate the project to their network of customers, members, and collaborators.</p> <p>A joint Press Release was launched in M1 to present the project goals and its partners.</p>	<p>Within the communication strategy, press releases can also target specific stakeholders depending on the journal/paper/website where the press release is published or distributed.</p>	ALL Stakeholders
Developer Community	<p>The project will connect and execute promotional activities in open communities and channels of developers, targeting those fostering openness and diversity, such as Gitter communities,</p>	<p>Widespread awareness, uptake, and validation among the developer community.</p>	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovators

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
	Women Who Code , Women in AI and Hashnode .		
Publishing and Scouting Platforms	Aside from publishing the open calls in the ' Competitive calls and calls for third parties ' platform of the EC, FOODITY will leverage pre-existing multi-stakeholder portals to promote the project and its open calls, such as EUcalls , CALLforEUROPE , EU Agenda or the ERA Portal Austria .	Widespread awareness among potential applicants to the Open Calls.	Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovation and Associations, Partnerships and Networks

Table 8. Communication - Promotional Material and Branding Elements

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Printing and Merchandising	This is the predominant element when participating in physical events and meetings, including brochures, flyers, posters, and other laid-out paper-based resources. The material will be available as e-files and printed when needed. In addition, FOODITY will explore using reusable merchandising as a creative measure that entices the audience to know the project.	Distributed at various events, conferences, workshops, etc., will gain the project visibility with the general public and the national and European media.	ALL Stakeholders
Slide Decks	Slide decks will sometimes replace the website as the project's 'Point of Market Entry', mainly in events, email campaigns and one-to-one meetings. FOODITY produced the initial slide deck; further	Project presentation to be shared with the broad audience of the project.	Food Value Chain, Entrepreneurs and Research Ecosystem, Social Innovation and Associations, Partnerships and

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
	versions will be provided to fine-tune content for the target audience and update achievements.		Networks, Policymakers
Infographics & Banners	Infographics and banners are eye-catching elements to quickly draw attention to the project, its objectives, announcements, partners, or the beneficiaries from the funding. Therefore, the project will design and produce these items regularly, integrating them into the website, social media, and newsletters.	Attractive visual content to be shared with the broad audience of the project.	ALL Stakeholders
Multimedia material	The project will produce at least 3 videos and use clips to have self-explanatory and appealing material for the website and social media, leveraging other available distribution channels of promotion (e.g., YouTube, Vimeo). Public webinars and live training modules will be recorded and made available.	Attractive visual content to be shared with the broad audience of the project.	ALL Stakeholders
Logo and Templates	FOODITY keeps a brand to be used, refined, and protected throughout the project. See brand elements in Annex B.	Common visual branding.	ALL Stakeholders

3.3 Dissemination and Communication Monitoring

Monitoring and adjusting the Dissemination and Communication plan on a frequent basis is a fundamental element of the project's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed.

It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. Emphasis is given to the pre-assessment of information needs, the monitoring frequency, and the method of collecting evidence.

The execution and effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is dependent on a close monitoring, flexible and prompt response mechanism. Every designed and implemented activity will be monitored and evaluated according to its account and closely related to the KPIs (see **ANNEX A: Dissemination and Communication KPIs**).

Figure 7. Dissemination & Communication Loop

- **Design:** Design is an activity based on the Dissemination and Communication Plan and the desired impact.
- **Execute:** Execute according to plan.
- **Monitor:** Closely monitor the activity and collect input and results. Monitoring will be based on a template that is available only to partners through the internal project's shared Drive.
- **Evaluate:** Evaluate the outcomes of the activity in a collaborative way according to the desired targets set in the design phase.
- **Learn:** Learn through this evaluation and try to extract the most valuable outcomes out of it.
- **Adjust:** Absorb findings and lessons learnt to adjust the plan accordingly, if needed.

All outcomes and results of the Dissemination and Communication plan will be reported in **D4.6 FOODITY Impact Interim Report** at Month 18 and **D4.7 FOODITY Impact Final Report** at Month 36.

3.3.1 Monitoring Strategy

To plan and keep track of all the dissemination and communication activities, the Dissemination and Communication Leader has designed a C&D Monitoring tool (Figure 8) that all partners can easily access and use through the project's internal Consortium Shared Repository Google Drive folder.

Communication and Dissemination activities are a collective effort that all partners need and should contribute to. Whenever a partner performs a communication or dissemination action/activity, it needs to be reported; otherwise, traceability is lost. For this reason, we have created a Communication and Dissemination monitoring document to list and report all efforts linked to the communication and dissemination of the project and its results, where all partners should provide their input on potential opportunities.

The monitoring tool, in Excel format, keeps track of every dissemination and communication action (foreseen or done) in the frame of FOODITY measuring the KPIs achievement and partner's involvement. It includes tabs such as:

- **Newsletters and Magazines** - To set the stage and achieve wider reach and visibility, a first approach will seek to contribute directly to existing newsletters/magazines with an already established audience in FOODITY's main fields of study. To do so, collaboration from all partners is required to identify those we might be able to work with. Hence, all partners should fill in the Newsletter and Magazines tab in the C&D database with those platforms they already have access to and/or those that may be interested in publishing and sharing articles or a one-pager about the project.
- **Peer-Reviewed publications and Practice abstracts** - The project is expected to deliver research publications in international journals and practice abstracts. This activity falls under the responsibility of FOODITY's research and technical partners, who should fill in both the Scientific Publications and Practice Abstracts tabs in the C&D database with those relevant to the project. When applicable, AUSTRALO will upload the Scientific Publications to the [FOODITY Zenodo community](#).
- **Events** - Whenever there is an opportunity to participate in a virtual or physical event to promote the project or any of its activities, partners should contact AUSTRALO to plan the promotional materials and content that may be needed. Partners should fill in the Events tabs in the C&D database with those upcoming/relevant to the project.

This resource will be a living document for the whole project duration, available to all partners in the Shared Drive at FOODITY - Consortium Shared Repository > WP4, as well as embedded into the FOODITY Mastersheet.

Partners are required to fill in the name and person in charge and the status of the activity (Opportunity, Confirmed, Cancelled, Done) in the tracker to follow up effectively on every action. Further tabs can be added to this document according to the project's needs.

CATEGORY	TITLE	DATE	DESCRIPTION	STATUS	PLATFORM	LINK	PARTNER
Website Post	FOOD and nutriTiOn Data-driven innovation respectful of citizen's Data Sovereignty: FOODITY	01/12/2022	Online reference to FOODITY by Development Aid	Done	Development Aid's website	https://www.developmentaid.org/organizations/awards/view/396518/food-and-nutrition-data-driven-innovation-respectful-of-citizen-s-data-sovereignty	-
Website Post	FOODITY: FOOD AND NUTRITION DATA-DRIVEN INNOVATION RESPECTFUL OF CITIZEN'S DATA SOVEREIGNTY	01/01/2023	Online reference to FOODITY by its partner ZSI	Done	ZSI's website + Social media	https://www.zsi.at/de/object/project/6462	ZSI
Website Post	FOODITY: Food and nutriTiOn Data-driven innovation respectful of citizen's Data Sovereignty	01/01/2023	Online reference to FOODITY by its partner AUSTRALO	Done	Open Aire's website	https://beopen.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_...he:e2a4c6fb9ae8e46c02	AUSTRALO
Press Release	FOODITY Project Launch Press Release	19/01/2023	Announcement of the official launch of FOODITY by its consortium	Done	Zenodo + Project's website + Social media	https://rebrand.ly/FOODITY-launchPR	AUSTRALO
Article	Foodity – Data driven solutions for food and nutrition respectful of citizen data sovereignty	19/01/2023	Announcement of the official launch of FOODITY by its partner SPLORO	Done	SPLORO's website + Social media	https://sploro.eu/foodity-2-million-euros-for-data-driven-food-solutions/	SPLORO
Website Post	FOODITY Project	19/01/2023	Online reference to FOODITY by its partner F6S	Done	F6S's website	https://www.f6s.com/foodity-project/about	F6S

Figure 8. FOODITY Monitoring Tool view

3.3.2 Possible Risks

There are several risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project (Table 9). **These risks will be monitored and mitigated** by the Communication and Dissemination leader, who will also control these risks on a regular basis and will report any changes to the Project Coordinator. Examples of communication risks include, but are not limited to:

Table 9. Dissemination and Communication Risks

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RISKS		
Risk	Priority	Measure to minimise the risk
Low participation in the open calls	Medium	If the reception of proposals does not meet the expected KPIs, to increase the dissemination activities to augment the number of proposals for the next call.

3.4 Dissemination and Communication Guidelines

Communication and dissemination efforts are essential to the success of FOODITY. Given their importance, all consortium partners must contribute to promoting its objectives, activities, and achievements. Therefore, the Dissemination and Communication Leader has prepared guidelines for the FOODITY consortium to have standard rules for communicating or disseminating project activities and results (see **ANNEX B: Dissemination and Communication Guidelines**).

4 Exploitation and Sustainability

Exploitation and sustainability activities are a consortium-coordinated effort to define the strategy to use FOODITY results for research or commercial purposes, particularly after the end of the project. More specifically, and according to the EC, exploitation involves: using results in further research activities beyond those covered by the project, developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, and creating and providing a service. Moreover, key exploitable results (KER)⁷ are those that are tangible or intangible outputs of the project (e.g., data, knowledge and information, whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected), which are generated in the project as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.

Within the framework of the project, exploitation includes the brainstorming of the legal framework to ensure the continuation of the activities developed within FOODITY towards increased data sovereignty in data-driven food and nutrition solutions, IPR questions, creation of feasible business models that can add value to future pilot beneficiaries, and development and review of revenue streams that could facilitate the financial sustainability of such activities.

An initial identification of exploitable results has been identified at the proposal stage, summarised in Table 10.

Table 10. FOODITY Key Exploitable Results

Key exploitable result	Responsible
FOODITY pilot development program, distributing 2M€ in funding to 12 teams, each receiving between 150k€ to 190k€ in funding.	Partner F6S, in charge of the programme methodology, will seek new funding possibilities as well as business models to finance the program.
12 pilots of data-driven solutions in the food and nutrition domain.	IPR developed by the pilots belongs to the beneficiaries that create them.
Library of AI-based software components as building blocks for the food and nutrition pilots.	Partner CERTH exploits these components as a result of the H2020 project PROTEIN with their respective licenses.
A platform consisting of infrastructure and application components to guarantee citizens' data rights.	Partner JIBE develops the platform and the commercial mode for its exploitation.
Data commons from data-driven solutions in food and nutrition benefitting food value chain actors.	Partner SOF develops the data lake and ensures interoperability with federated infrastructure to publish the data.

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/informatics/items/689551>

Key exploitable result	Responsible
Engagement mechanism of over 200 citizens in expressing their concerns.	Partner ZSI develops the PhotoWorkshop methodology for the engagement of citizens in solutions development.

Considering the results mentioned above and others that emerge during the implementation of the project, the exploitation and commercialisation strategy will consider several steps, as briefly described below.

1. **Identification of Key Exploitable Results:** As mentioned above, these are the tangible and intangible outputs of the project. This step will consist in identifying all relevant KER and, for each, first detailing in which project activity (e.g., WP, Task) it was developed, what the KER is, any relevant protection considerations (e.g., open access, patentable), TRL, and KER owner(s). Secondly, for each KER, it will be identified for what problems it is valuable, its unique selling points/value proposition, target market, competitors (if any), and exploitation route, among other aspects.
2. **Impact assessment with potentially interested stakeholders:** The impact assessment will aim to understand how the KERs are experienced or may be used by different stakeholders. Stakeholders may include the third parties participating in the FOODITY pilot programme, citizens, and policymakers.
3. **Individual exploitation plans:** These plans will describe for each partner the main results developed by them and their value, the interest in results that have been designed or created by other partners and plans to exploit these results.
4. **Joint exploitation plans:** These will describe the potential collaboration between one or more partners and any exploitation intentions around a common result.

Also, regarding the exploitation of the solutions developed within the framework of the FOODITY pilot programme, the 12 projects will be requested to reflect on (and receive support from the partners) on how their solution can be exploited and become sustainable after the end of the funding period. The funded projects will be required to reflect on their value proposition, the market analysis and competition, potential business and revenue model, and how to upscale their solution to a higher TRL post-project funding.

5 Conclusions

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation in Horizon Europe projects are structured to ensure that projects have an impact beyond the research outcomes. To this end, **FOODITY has developed the Impact Master Plan, which outlines the most important strategy** that must be considered throughout the project's lifetime. The current document is expected to act as a point of reference for current and foreseen communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, while all mentioned activities will be continuously monitored and updated throughout the project's lifetime.

Regarding communication and dissemination, FOODITY aims to publicise the project's outcomes, in its different phases, to the right audiences at the right time to demonstrate how research and innovation are contributing to a 'European Innovation Union'. Communication activities will show our multidisciplinary European consortium's achievements in scientific excellence and contribution to competitiveness. In addition, the plan has been made keeping in mind the interdisciplinary nature of FOODITY members, which allows them to reach very different and well-targeted segments of the identified stakeholders. Channels have been chosen to accomplish more comprehensive visibility and boost the project through some of the most common means of communication nowadays, such as social networks, events, papers, conferences, or email marketing. At the same time, public relations campaigns have been planned to keep all related stakeholders updated on FOODITY's progress and results. All these actions must be done under the designed project's identity and by spreading the right messages so that every communication released to the audience is coherent with the scope of the whole project. To make sure all these procedures are carried out properly, a system of metrics has been designed to measure the obtained results and compare them with the previously set objectives.

Regarding exploitation, the **FOODITY consortium will continuously monitor and evaluate the project's outcomes**, examine possible exploitation routes, and identify the most prominent exploitation pathway for each individual asset. In addition, various possible routes, such as individual and/or joint exploitation, scientific vs commercial exploitation etc., will be examined to define the optimum way to go forward and generate impact beyond the closed borders of the project.

ANNEX A: Dissemination and Communication KPIs

Table 11. Dissemination KPIs

DISSEMINATION KPIs		
Measure	Indicator	Target
Peer-reviewed publications	N° of peer-reviewed scientific articles	10
Awareness publications	N° of publications in articles, blog posts, insight papers, citizen factsheets and others	30
Practice abstracts	N° of practice abstracts collected	50
Open Access Research	Downloads of open access materials	> 1000
Webinars/workshops	No. of Webinars / Workshops to (co-)organise:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How-to-apply webinars/info sessions (2 per open call) 	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal workshops to support beneficiaries (3 per open call/ round) 	6
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events targeting citizen empowerment processes 	6
Conferences/ fairs	Participation and presentation of the project at events	30

Table 12. Communication KPIs

COMMUNICATION KPIs		
Measure	Indicator	Target
E-mail campaigns	Broadcasting messages to a database of contact points	>5,000
1-to-1 meetings (Synergies / collaborations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up collaboration with at least 5 EU-funded projects. • Promote the open calls among 20+ innovation ecosystems. • Create synergies with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3+ EU associations ○ 5+ EU DIHs 	33
Project website	> 500 unique visitors/ month (average)	500
Open calls platform	Receive over 50 successful applications in each call	100
Social Media	Focus on Twitter and LinkedIn	2,500
Newsletters	Develop quarterly newsletters (4x3=12) + contribute to 6 external newsletters	18
Press releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint press release at M01. • Regular PR through partners. 	-

COMMUNICATION KPIS		
Measure	Indicator	Target
Printing/merch.	Distribution of hard copies (brochures, flyers, other paper resources)	>1,500
Infographics and banners	Development of graphic elements	>100
Multimedia	The project will produce at least 3 videos and use clips to have self-explanatory and appealing material for the website / social media	3
Success stories	Highlighting the work of the third parties	-

ANNEX B: Dissemination and Communication Guidelines

Communication and dissemination efforts are essential to FOODITY's success. Given their importance, all consortium partners must contribute to promoting its objectives, activities, and achievements. These guidelines will help you with this task. Take a look!

*To share your communication and dissemination updates and address any questions or suggestions about them or these guidelines, please contact us at foodity@australo.org.

Contents

- **Internal communication**
- **External communication**
 - Website
 - Social media
 - Partners and EU organisation's social media profiles
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 - Participation in events
 - Technical and scientific publications
 - Open access repository
- **Project materials and brand identity elements**
 - The project in a nutshell
 - Brand elements
 - PPT and Word templates
 - Imagery
- **GDPR compliance**
- **EU logo, acknowledgement and disclaimer**

Internal communication

The main internal communication channels of the FOODITY project, where information related to dissemination and communication activities will be shared, are:

- **Email**
 - **FOODITY partners contacts**, included in the FOODITY Mastersheet (Partner Contacts tab — saved in the internal Consortium Shared Repository Google Drive folder).
 - **General FOODITY mailing list**: foodity-general@f6s.com
 - **WP 4** (Outreach and Open Calls Management) **representatives contact list**, saved in the internal Marketing Monitoring document (FOODITY Consortium Shared Repository > WP4 - WP4 Representatives tab) and being continuously updated.
 - **FOODITY Slack**, where we can communicate via chat, audio, or video calls. *Access is provided on request to the project coordinator (samuel@f6s.com). Here, we have created the #dissemination-communication channel, where we can share quick updates, documents and materials related to those activities.
 - **FOODITY Consortium Shared Repository**: The shared platform to store all project documents to which partners must have access. *The communication and dissemination materials will be saved in the WP4 + 06. Logo + Branding materials + 09. Promotional materials folders. The material that can be shared publicly will also be uploaded to the project's open-access repository, [Zenodo](#).
 - **FOODITY Consortium Meetings**: They are being held on a bi-weekly basis since February 2023 (from 10am to 11am on Tuesdays). *Invitation is provided on request to the project coordinator (samuel@f6s.com).
 - **WP4 meetings**: All task leaders from WP4 and, if possible, one representative from each partner organisation should always be present whenever a WP4 is scheduled.
- **At least one person from your organisation must be active in these channels and attend our WP 4 calls!**

External communication

Website

FOODITY's website: <https://foodity.eu/>

In addition to providing a general overview of the project, the website will be continuously updated to share FOODITY's progress, activities and achievements, and to promote its open calls and their outcomes, as well as our consortium among external stakeholders.

As a partner, you must contribute to populating the website by sending us your content regularly to foodity@australo.org.

The content could be about:

- your organisation's participation in project-related scientific publications, events, workshops, conferences, awards ceremonies, etc.,
- the main scientific and technical achievements of the project,
- news related to a given WP/task.

Social media

[Twitter](#): @FOODITY_EU
[LinkedIn](#): @FOODITY
[YouTube](#): @FOODITY_EU

We kindly invite you to follow FOODITY's social media accounts — both via your organisation's profiles and the personal profiles of the team members involved in the project.

Also, please remember to always mention them in your posts about the project and engage (click, share, comment, react, save) with our updates!

- **Content**

In all FOODITY social channels, we will share content about the solutions we are working on (goals, results, facts, methodology), the partners involved, the project's latest updates, news, and events, as well as interesting external information and resources (articles, events, initiatives, videos, newsletters, reports, eBooks, infographics) relevant to our audience and sector:

- On **Twitter**, we will share more real-time information on events, developments, and external content.
- On **LinkedIn**, we will focus on sharing information about the project and its partners.

- On **YouTube**, we will upload the project's videos, webinars, online events, and interviews.

Your FOODITY posts could also be about:

- your progress and collaborative work with other partners,
- your participation in project related meetings, events, workshops and conferences,
- your organisation's latest news and publications related to FOODITY,
- interesting external resources related to the topic of the project.

● **Tone**

We recommend that you talk about the project in a clear, concise, informal, engaging, and positive way.

- use simple and approachable language,
- make creative and innovative content,
- and don't be afraid to use humour and be entertaining!

● **Hashtags to use in your posts**

- **#FOODITY**: When talking about the project on channels where it doesn't have an account and can't be mentioned (out of Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube).
- **#FOODITYnews**: When sharing news about the project.
- **#FOODITYteam**: When talking about the organisations and people involved in the project. / **#FOODITYinnovators**: When talking about the candidates selected in our open calls.
- Related to the project's sector and subject:
 - #FoodSystems #NutritionSystems #FoodSecurity #FoodSafety #Food2030 #EUFood #EUFoodSafety #EUGreenDeal #EUBiodiversity #SustainableNutrition #SustainableFoodSystems #Food #Nutrition #Health #HealthyDiet #SustainableDiet #NutritionSolutions #AgrifoodSystems #ClimateChange #ClimateCrisis #ClimateAction #Sustainability #Circularity #CircularEconomy #SDGs #SocialInnovation #SustainableInnovation #SustainableFoodSystems #CitizenEmpowerment
 - #DigitalSolutions #DigitalTransition #DigitalTransformation #DigitalTechnology #Technology #Digitalization #DataSolutions #DataSovereignty #DataEconomy #OpenSource #OpenAccess #DigitalRights #OpenData #DataGovernance #DataManagement #DataInnovation #OpenScience #DataRights

- #OpenCalls #FSTP #PilotProgramme #Funding #Mentoring #Coaching
#Training #RTOs #SMEs #Startups #NGOs #SocialInnovators #FoodIndustry
- #EUFunded #EUFunding #HorizonEU #HorizonEurope #Research #EUresearch
#Innovation #Research #Science #EUResearch #EUInnovation
- Recommended number of hashtags to use per channel:
 - Twitter: 1-2
 - LinkedIn: 1-5
 - YouTube: 3-5
 - Instagram: 3-5
 - Facebook: 2-3

Partners and EU organisations social media profiles

Social media profiles to communicate with or mention in our posts about FOODITY so that they have a wider reach.

- **Partners**

Twitter	LinkedIn	Facebook	Instagram
@f6s	F6S, F6S Innovation	F6S	-
@AustraloTeam	AUSTRALO	-	-
@JibeCompany	Jibe Company	Jibe Company	@jiberomania
@sploro_eu	Sploro	-	-
@SofteamGroup	SOFTEAM	-	-
@CERTHellas	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)	@CERTHellas	-
@ZSIInnovation	Centre for Social Innovation	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation - ZSI	-

- **EU organisations**

Twitter	LinkedIn	Facebook	Instagram
@EU_Commission	European Commission	European Commission	@europeancommission
@HorizonEU	-	Horizon Europe	@horizoneurope
@EUScienceInnov	EU Science, Research and Innovation	EU Science & Innovation Brussels	EU Science (@eu_science)
@EU_HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)	-	-
@REA_research	European Research Executive Agency (REA)	REA Research Executive Agency	-
@DigitalEU	EU Digital & Tech	Digital EU	DigitalEU
@EUeic, @EU_EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency	-
@EUFIC	European Food Information Council (EUFIC)	EUFIC - European Food Information Council	European Food Information Council
@SciFoodHealth	SciFoodHealth	-	-

→ Do you know of other social media profiles that could be useful for the project? Send them to foodity@australo.org, and we will include them in this document and our internal Marketing Monitoring document (Community & Social Media tab), at the Consortium Shared Repository Google Drive.

Newsletters

If your organisation is going to include information about FOODITY in a newsletter, please tell us about it at foodity@australo.org at least two weeks in advance so that we can share the information and materials you may need.

- Once the newsletter has been sent, you can report it in the project's Marketing Monitoring document (Editorial Calendar tab), so that we can have a record of the newsletters in which it has appeared.
- Also, add all other online references your organisation makes about the project in this document (in your organisation's website, the press, journals, blogs, etc.).

PR material

FOODITY PR material will be available in the project's promotional materials folder at the project's Shared Google Drive. The most relevant material will also be published on the project website and [Zenodo](#).

PR material will be available in online and printed formats whenever necessary (e.g., for events, conventions, workshops) — by AUSTRALO or other project partners, depending on volume and logistics.

This material, whether in electronic or hard copy format, must always include:

- FOODITY social media ([Twitter](#) + [LinkedIn](#)) and [website](#) links.
- [FOODITY logo](#) and [EU emblem](#).
- EU-funding statement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101086105.

Merchandising

For any merchandising material your organisation may need to print or produce, please request a free quote from several suppliers (at least three) before placing your order. In any case, please [contact us](#) beforehand to assist with designs and other related tasks.

Participation in events

If your organisation is going to participate in an event, conference, webinar, workshop or meeting that can impact FOODITY, please let us know at foodity@australo.org within at least two weeks' notice so that we can prepare a communication campaign and promote it on the project's channels. We can also inform the rest of the consortium members so they can promote it among their community and participate.

Steps to take when participating in events:

1. BEFORE the event

- Inform [FOODITY's communication team](#) at least two weeks in advance.
- Mention FOODITY and tag its accounts when promoting the event on social media.
- Use FOODITY's PPT template (available at the Shared Google Drive) if you are representing the project. You can use your company's template if you are just mentioning it in your presentation. Still, you must indicate you are part of FOODITY.
 - Add the [FOODITY logo](#) and the [EU emblem](#) with the acknowledgement: FOODITY has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101086105.

2. DURING the event

- Publish content about it on social media, mentioning FOODITY and tagging its accounts.
- You can also share content (text + graphic material) with us so we can publish it on FOODITY's accounts.

3. AFTER the event

- Report your participation in the project's Marketing Monitoring document (Events tab).
- Create a blog post about your participation in the event — with the main highlights and takeaways, interesting stories, and data.
- Send the blog post to foodity@australo.org so we can publish it on FOODITY website and social media.
- Share pictures, videos and materials from the event with us. You can save them in our events participation folder at the Shared Drive (there, create a folder with the event's name) and let us know by email so we can share them in our channels.

Technical and scientific publications

→ Please send your organisation's technical and scientific publications about FOODITY to foodity@australo.org two weeks before publishing them so that we can review them.

Once they're published, include them in the project's Marketing Monitoring document, Scientific Publications tab, at the project's Shared Drive.

We welcome all partners to identify and propose opportunities to publish technical outcomes (articles, workshops, congresses).

Open access repository

The FOODITY open access repository is available at [Zenodo](#).

Please send the papers, articles, press releases and other public materials you create in the project context to foodity@australo.org so we can publish them on [Zenodo](#), the open-access repository for the project.

*The European Commission has launched [Open Research Europe \(ORE\)](#), an open-access platform for research from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and Euratom funding across all subject areas.

ORE upholds the principles of open science by publishing articles immediately, followed by transparent and open peer review, including supporting data and materials. Reviewers' names are public, as are their reviews, which are also citable. Article-level metrics continuously track the scientific and societal impact of publications. In short, ORE gives everyone, researchers and citizens alike, free access to the latest scientific discoveries.

Publishing in ORE is optional. The European Commission covers all costs upfront, so there is no author's fee or administrative burden. In addition, automatic compliance with Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe open access requirements is guaranteed. Lastly, ORE is also a solution to publish articles even after the Horizon Europe grant has ended.

Project materials and brand identity elements

Some of the materials presented below will be modified and enriched according to the project's needs.

The project in a nutshell

You can use this FOODITY description in different contexts, such as emails, presentations, social media, websites, etc.

Data-driven solutions for food and nutrition respectful of citizen data sovereignty.

The main goal of FOODITY is to create a European ecosystem of digital solutions that contributes to a more sustainable and healthy food and nutrition system — respecting citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty.

FOODITY will run a **2M€ pilot development programme for creating 12 data-driven solutions** to demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while guaranteeing the user's full control and ownership over their personal data.

These innovations will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the four Food 2030 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: (1) Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (2) Food systems supporting a healthy planet, (3) Circularity and resource efficiency, and (4) Innovation and empowering communities.

Participants in the pilot development programme will be selected through **two open calls** to be **launched in the second semester of 2023**. The programme will provide its beneficiaries with a set of value-added services: from one-to-one mentoring to training on technical, business, and legal matters, as well as technical and financial support (up to 187.500€ per beneficiary) for developing their pilots.

During the next three years (January 2023 - December 2025), the **FOODITY** consortium, comprised of 7 partners, will join forces to make this a reality.

FOODITY has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101086105.

For more information, visit <https://foodity.eu/>

Brand elements

FOODITY brand elements include its name, logo, fonts, and colours that you must use in all communication and dissemination activities about the project.

Project name: FOODITY

The name of the project must be written in capital letters.

Logo

You can download the FOODITY logo from [Zenodo](#).

Versions: Main + Black/White.

It is unalterable, so it is strictly forbidden to modify it in any way.

It must be visible in its entirety and placed on a background that does not compromise its integrity. In addition, it must always be surrounded by a free space or a protected area where no other element (text, image, drawing, figure, etc.) can infringe on it.

When adding the logo to your company's website or any other online platform, please link it to the [project website](#).

There are a few things to consider when using its different versions:

- Whenever possible, the main logo should always be preferred.
- If the background on which it is to be placed has a medium colour or the gradient of the brand (purple to magenta), the white logo should be preferred.
- The black logo should only be used when colour is not available (i.e., black & white printing, embossing on specific materials, laser etching, etc.).

Fonts

- Titles: **Josefin Sans Bold** - [download](#).
- Longer texts: **Open Sans** - [download](#).

Colours

- **Primary**
 - **Dark purple: #78056C**
 - **Magenta: #FF638A**

- **Secondary**
 - **Yellow: #FFFA5A**
 - **Orange: #FC751A**
 - **Dark purple: #5B2549**
 - **Light purple: #B6A5F9**

- **Neutrals**
 - **White: #FFFFFF**
 - **Grey: #5E5359**

PPT and Word templates

PPT and Word templates including all FOODITY brand elements can be found in the Project Templates folder at the project's Shared Drive.

You can use these templates to promote FOODITY in meetings and events. Remember to export their PDF version when presenting!

Imagery

To avoid copyright issues with the images you use in your project communications, it is best to use Creative Commons licensed images, or free-for-commercial use/no attribution required images that can be found in online image libraries.

1. Creative Commons licenses are a set of copyright licenses that offer the creator of a work a simple way to give the public permission to share and use their work under their terms and conditions.

These licenses are composed of four features:

- Attribution (BY) requires referencing the original author.
- Share Alike (SA) allows derivative works to be made under the same or a similar license.
- Non-Commercial (NC) obliges that the work is not used for commercial purposes.
- No Derivative Works (ND) does not allow the work to be modified in any way.

Free images for commercial use that you can use without risking legal problems are:

- Images whose author has given you written permission.
 - Images that have a Creative Commons 0 or CC0 License. The CC0 License indicates that they are public domain images, and you can use them freely for commercial use, modifying them without the need to refer to their author.
2. When using image libraries, make sure that their images indicate that they are free for commercial use or no attribution is required, like in this example:

3. You can find suitable images for the communication of the project in online free image libraries, such as:

- [Google images](#)

Google is a good place to start searching for images since results will include photos from Flickr and other stock photography sites.

In the advanced image search, enter keywords and specify the size, aspect ratio and other details about the image you need. At the end of the form, select the usage rights that apply. Once you've found an image you like, click through to the page to double-check its licence.

- [The Stocks](#)
- [Unsplash](#)
- [Gratisography](#)
- [Death to the Stock Photo](#)
- [Reshot](#)
- [ISO Republic](#)
- [Pixabay](#)
- [Canva](#)
- [ShotStash](#)
- [FreePhotos](#)
- [Picjumbo](#)
- [Pexels](#)
- [Barnimages](#)

GDPR compliance

GDPR compliance is crucial for many of the activities within the project (newsletters, webinars, bootcamps, interviews, etc.).

The EU GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) applies to everybody who handles the personal data of European citizens. The legislation gives individuals rights over what organisations do with their data and includes strict fines for organisations that fail to comply.

Newsletters

1. Data permission

Data permission is about how we manage email opt-ins (people who subscribe to our newsletters). We cannot assume that they want to be contacted according to the GDPR. Leads, customers and partners need to confirm that they want to be contacted explicitly. Therefore, a pre-ticked box automatically opts them in and won't cut it anymore — people must confirm they want to be contacted deliberately. Example of the form we can use:

Don't miss out! [Subscribe to our newsletter and stay updated](#)

Enter your email address to subscribe*

Enter your first name*

Enter your last name*

I agree to receive these newsletters and accept the data privacy statement

You may unsubscribe at any time using the link in our newsletter.

 We use Sendinblue as our marketing platform. By Clicking below to submit this form, you acknowledge that the information you provided will be transferred to Sendinblue for processing in accordance with their [terms of use](#)

SUBSCRIBE

2. Data access

Our subscribers must be able to access their data. Also, the right to be forgotten allows them to have obsolete or inaccurate personal data deleted.

For us, it can be as simple as including an unsubscribe link in our newsletters and mailings and linking it to where users can manage their email preferences.

Example:

3. Data focus

Try to avoid collecting any unnecessary data and stick with the basics.

GDPR-compliant online events

Key GDPR-related aspects to consider when creating an event registration form:

- Don't collect more information than you need to. For example, information about the gender of participants is sensitive and does not always need to be collected. One option could be to make responding to these types of fields optional.
- When indicating how participants can exercise their rights, include an email address in use and monitored regularly.
- Be transparent about why you are collecting data and with whom you will share it.

Public consultations

Public consultations often collect personal data to use in a consultation. Therefore, the collection and further processing of such data will fall within the scope of the GDPR.

Even if the data is simply collected and stored, with no active steps taken to "use" it, the conditions set by the GDPR will still apply. For example, you must ensure adequate data security or that no more data is retained than necessary.

EU logo, acknowledgement and disclaimer

EU logo and acknowledgement

As recipients of EU funding, we have to use the [EU emblem](#) in our communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programs.

You can adapt this acknowledgement text depending on what you need to deliver or submit.

EU disclaimer

It is also necessary to include a disclaimer in any document you have to deliver within the scope of the project — a statement that denies liability and is intended to prevent civil liability arising from certain acts or omissions.

The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Text can appear on the right, left, bottom, or top, depending on your needs, and in various fonts.

For more information, please follow the [guidelines on using the EU emblem](#) in the context of EU funding and apply the indicated [graphic rules](#).

ANNEX C: Website and Social Media Channels

Website

Within the dissemination and communication activities of the project, the FOODITY website has been created at <https://foodity.eu/>, with the following structure:

- **Home** (<https://foodity.eu/>) — Including the project’s tagline, main objectives, pilot development programme, value proposal for Open Calls participants, expected impact, and consortium, along with a call to action to subscribe to its Newsletter and the EU funding and Privacy Policy and Terms of Use disclaimers.

FOODITY is an impact-driven project funded under the Horizon Europe programme involving 7 partners from 9 countries.

Over the next 3 years (2023 - 2026), we will work together to ensure a dynamic ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition that respect citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty in Europe.

Data for the people Data for the planet

We are convinced that the data economy offers great opportunities to improve food systems.

With the right data-driven technology, citizens can influence the overall environmental impact of food systems and the quality of diets that system actors (producers, distributors, retailers) offer to consumers. How? By demanding better, healthier, and more environmentally friendly food choices.

However, most popular tools and platforms (e.g. wearables and software applications) are closed and limit citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty and transferability.

At FOODITY, we are on a mission

to create a dynamic European ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition respectful of citizens' right to personal data sovereignty – and demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovations in this area, engaging citizens in their development.

How?

Through our FOODITY pilot development programme

2M€

pilot development programme

178K€

Support of up to 187.500€ per beneficiary

2

open calls

12

data-driven innovations

We will run a **2M€** pilot development programme funding **12** industry and research collaborations for data-driven innovations in food and nutrition.

Participants will be selected through **two open calls** to be launched in **the second semester of 2023**.

Value-added services for participants to develop their pilots

Financial support up to **187.500€** per beneficiary

Technology access and **technical support**

One-to-one business mentoring

Group coaching

Training on technical, business, and legal matters

For who? The FOODITY innovators

We are looking for:

- Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and universities
- Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups
- Social innovation actors, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and citizen associations
- Training organisations focused on the food industry

Don't miss a thing

Learn more about our project and our open calls

[About The Project](#)

[Open Calls](#)

Subscribe to our [newsletter](#) and follow us on social media to be updated on our upcoming opportunities and everything FOODITY-related. And if you have any questions, [contact us!](#)

Our impact

The open call projects will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the Food 2030 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities:

- Food systems supporting a healthy planet
- Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets
- Circularity and resource efficiency
- Innovation and empowering communities

"FOODITY has the ingredients to make a significant difference in how citizens use and control their personal data, leading to better and more sustainable decisions. We are confident that our pilot programme and funded solutions will show how increased control over personal data can lead to better personal nutrition choices and also contribute with knowledge to ensure more sustainable food systems."

Samuel Almeida, FOODITY's Project Coordinator.

The FOODITY team

This ambitious 36-month project brings together seven multidisciplinary partners from different EU member states who have joined forces to make it a reality.

7 organizations | 9 countries | 1 team | 36 months

From top-level experts in ICT-based solutions for the food and nutrition sector (CERTH), technologies for user's control of personal data (JIBE) and integration of data commons into federated infrastructure (SOFTEAM), to experienced professionals in engaging citizens (F6S, AUSTRALO and SPLORO) and social innovation (ZSI).

[Meet Our Team](#)

News & events

Stay updated on our latest news, stories, activities and upcoming events.

Subscribe to our newsletter

[Subscribe](#)

[Privacy Policy](#) | [Terms of Use](#)

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Specific sections have been dedicated to:

- **The project** (<https://foodity.eu/about/>) — explaining FOODITY’s key aspects, mission, vision and main impact results it will achieve.

The data provided by personalised food and nutrition solutions – from wearables to apps – has enabled people to eat healthier diets by suggesting tailored meal plans. But there is also an opportunity to use this data to **empower citizens to make better dietary choices**, including more environmentally friendly options. This can be achieved, for example, by informing them about the greenhouse gas emissions of the products they consume and suggesting ways to reduce them.

In addition to benefiting the individual citizen, **this data can improve the entire food system value chain**, as its actors (producers, distributors, retailers) can also use it to create more sustainable processes. **All this contributes to reducing emissions from the food sector while ensuring healthy diets.**

What is the main challenge in data-driven innovation? **Existing popular tools and platforms are closed and limit citizens’ rights to sovereignty and transferability of their personal data.** This restricts the possibility of using them for the common good, even if users consent to share their anonymised personal data.

Our mission

Our purpose is to enable a dynamic ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition that respects citizens’ right to personal data sovereignty in Europe.

To this end, we will run a **€2 million pilot development programme.** Our objective? **To fund 12 solutions** demonstrating the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while ensuring complete user control over their personal data.

Our programme beneficiaries will be able to use tools and software components from two recent research & innovation Horizon 2020-funded actions as building blocks for the development of their pilots.

The main impact results we will achieve

- Higher availability of shared data for increased competitiveness and sustainability of food system actors.
- Citizens in charge of their own data related to food and nutrition.
- Increased adoption of data-driven solutions for food and nutrition.
- Engaging citizens in food systems that are environmentally friendly and oriented towards healthy diets.

Impact outcomes

- **Open Calls** (<https://foodity.eu/open-calls/>) — specific section dedicated to explaining the main aspects of the project’s open calls, such as eligible applicants, funding and support offer, and objectives.

Who are we looking for? The FOODITY innovators

The eligible beneficiaries of our programme are:

Research and Technology Organisations (RTO) and universities

working to advance the state of the art and solve the challenges around data-driven innovation for food and nutrition, as well as working on mechanisms to preserve citizens' sovereignty over their personal data in using food and nutrition solutions.

Small or Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups

developing solutions for data-driven innovation, including personalised nutrition solutions for online food retail and delivery.

Social innovation actors, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and citizen associations

aiming at citizen empowerment, proposing concrete actions for raising awareness of citizens' data rights, and representing consumers' interest in food and nutrition.

Training organisations

providing professional training for careers in the food industry, such as culinary or nutrition schools interested in teaching and experimenting with the power of data for innovation and competitiveness in food production and diet planning.

What's in it for you? The FOODITY capacity building programme

Our programme beneficiaries will receive support from technical and business perspectives.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

Up to 187.500€ per beneficiary.

ACCESS TO TECHNOLOGY

Technology access and technical support to develop their solutions.

EXPERT MENTORING

Advice on business development: from marketing and sales to financing, innovation strategy or sustainability.

GROUP COACHING

Including mutual exchange between the open call beneficiaries.

TECHNICAL TRAINING

Training on relevant technical, business, and legal issues.

- **Team** (<https://foodity.eu/team/>) — where the members of the project's consortium are identified.
- **News** (<https://foodity.eu/news/>) — where the main updates, interviews and events of the project are being published.

- **Contact** (<https://foodity.eu/contact/>) — including options to contact the FOODITY team to ask questions, explore possible synergies, invite us to events, workshops or conferences, as well as to send us media and public relations enquiries.

CTAs to follow the project in social media channels and subscribe to its newsletter are included throughout the site.

Social Media

FOODITY maintains an active presence in social media channels, with particular focus on:

[LinkedIn:](#)

[Twitter:](#)

